

The lack of certainty in the Ecuadorian government

Abstract:

Ecuador grapples with political instability as President Guillermo Lasso's term faces premature termination amidst corruption allegations. This abstract outlines the cascade of events leading to the dissolution of legislative and executive powers under the controversial "Muerte Cruzada" decree. It highlights the erosion of public trust, bureaucratic complexities, and economic implications, emphasizing the urgent need for institutional reform. As Ecuador navigates a tumultuous transition, this abstract underscores the imperative of fostering accountability and restoring confidence in governance to pave the way for a more stable future.

It is no news that Ecuador has undergone multiple changes in government throughout its political existence. From 1976 to 2007, they had over 13 different presidents, whereas the norm dictates there should have been only seven, each serving a four-year term. During these thirty years, Ecuador experienced significant economic changes, the most drastic being the transition from its currency, the sucre, to the US dollar; territorial instability with the Paquisha conflict and the Cenepa War; and political changes with two military dictatorships under Guillermo Rodríguez Lara from 1972 to 1976 and then 1976–1979.

Currently, Ecuador is once again facing uncertainty in its presidential office. Guillermo Lasso was elected in 2021 with dreams and hopes of bringing positive change to the country. However, his government soon faced an impeachment process. The question arises as to why this president's term is ending prematurely.

It all began when a renowned Venezuelan journalist and his group of colleagues reported cases of corruption within the government. Public positions and million-dollar contracts were allegedly obtained through bribery rather than offering the best deals for the country. Lasso's brother-in-law allegedly had control over these irregularities. The journalist provided over 35,000 documents supporting these claims and approached the legislative body to denounce these irregularities. It is presumed that these illicit connections trace back to previous governments. The same journal published a phone call that one of the suspects in the case had with the journalist. The call revealed the operational details of the corrupt system.ⁱ Lasso defended his brother-in-law on multiple occasions stating “Danilo Carrera is a person whom I greatly esteem. I have known him for 64 years. He is an honorable, impeccable man, and his integrity and honor should not be compromised by using his face to create a logo symbolizing corruption”ⁱⁱ. To which he later stated that “the President of the Republic does not cover up for anyone.”ⁱⁱⁱ

During this period, there was also involvement with the Albanese mafia; there were apparently some connections with the involved parties in the corrupt scheme and during the investigations into the death of Ruben Cherres, one of the ex-leaders of the public companies that were under scrutiny. The connection between them apparently started when he got to prison and became the operator of this mafia, which was being investigated on a document called "Leon de Troya" that was later closed to protect the president's public image and then re-opened again by the prosecutor's office^{iv}. There was a close relationship with more than

12 companies between Cherres and Djika Dritan, an Albanian citizen who was in jail for narco-trafficking. Eight of the companies were constituted in one day. The same journal states that Cherres apparently reunited himself in Manta, a city in Ecuador, where he was planning on sending drugs under the name of a fishing company. Why is Guayaquil so attractive to drug cartels? ^vIs between Peru and Colombia. Countries that are in charge of producing drugs will send them to Guayaquil, which is the seaport, and these narcotics will later go to Europe and the US.

As a result, the legislative branch initiated a political trial against the president for bribery, corruption, embezzlement, and unlawful enrichment, all of which are stated as constitutional violations^{vi}. The constitutional court accepted the process when it started, but on May 17 of this year, the president took decisive action by issuing Decree No. 741. The decree invoked a legal provision known as "Muerte Cruzada" (Crossed Death)^{vii}, which dissolved the legislative and executive powers. The president justified this action by alleging that the legislators had hindered the implementation of his development plan, resulting in a political crisis and internal turmoil.

Now, the question on the minds of many Ecuadorians and the international community is: what will happen to this country? According to the 2008 Constitution, under this legal provision, the current president, Guillermo Lasso, can still govern under the oversight of the Constitutional Court via law decrees related to economic urgency^{viii}. The National Electoral Council (CNE), responsible for organizing, directing, and transparently overseeing elections, must call for elections, announce the results, and seat the winners in their respective positions. The CNE is also tasked with appointing members to the electoral organization's^{ix}. Once the elections are called, within a maximum of seven days, the incumbent or former legislators who did not complete their term and wish to participate again must declare their intention to run with their respective political parties. Guillermo Lasso could also announce himself as a presidential candidate, although this seems unlikely as he stated during a press conference that he will not run again^x. Once all the preparations are in place, the elections must be held within 90 days of the announcement^{xi}. The winners will be declared in the following days. If none of the candidates for the presidency receives a majority of votes, a second round will be held with only the two most-voted ticket pairs^{xii}. The winning pair will then assume leadership of the country.

What are the downfalls and consequences of not finishing the presidential mandate? The situation in Ecuador has several impacts on both Ecuadorians and the international community. Firstly, it highlights a lack of political stability, which undermines confidence in the government and impedes the country's progress. Zahid Hussain explains that governmental turmoil causes fewer investments; on the other hand, poor economic performance can cause the deterioration of the administration. This author also mentions that all democratic regimes are not stable, but not having to worry about it can cause citizens to concentrate on investing, working, and saving. Political stability also signifies a lack of competition, which can be dangerous and cause abuses by the government^{xiii}. This is not the case for Ecuador, which had sixteen presidential candidates in the 2021 elections and different heads of state from the same political party for thirteen years.

Secondly, the mandatory nature of voting, along with the potential fines imposed on non-compliance, create overwhelming voting obligations for Ecuadorian citizens. As an example of the bureaucracy in this country, Article 277, Inc. 1, of the Organic Law, the democracy code states that the institution that doesn't require the citizens to present the voting certificate or pay the imposed fine will lead to the employers of this entity being fined from one to ten wages, which can range from 450 to 4500 dollars^{xiv}. Prior articles also state that it is mandatory for a voting booth to attend the mandatory workshops where all the rules are explained; if not, there is also a penalty of 10 percent of the minimum wage^{xv}. It was also declared in 2021 by executive decree No. 85 that the voting certificate was not required and that it was prohibited to ask for it during any process unless there was a special law that asked for it because it is known that all this information is obtained through government internal programs^{xvi}. Now there is a discrepancy between this decree and what was required; one of the conditions for receiving payments from MIES—another Ecuadorian institution—is to show the voting certificate^{xvii}, another requisite where this paper is needed to enroll at a state university^{xviii}. Now, if you did not vote and want to study at a public university, you cannot unless you pay the mandatory fine, even if there was a decree that says the opposite. This is sadly a reality of many Ecuadorian administrative processes.

Thirdly, the failure of elected candidates to fulfill their promised projects and proposals erodes public trust in the political system^{xix}, leading to disillusionment among the electorate even though he had a successful vaccination system and making him win more acceptance from the opposition. He also installed an anticorruption secretary, which has now had no secretary for around six months since the article about corruption came out. The ex-secretary, before leaving, presented a paper where it showed that three public entities had an unloyal group that asked for "contributions" to get benefits and accepted contracts without technical and functional necessity. This was all part of the documentation used against the president. Another part of the presidential proposal was to give 20,000 houses to help economically disadvantaged individuals, but he only gave 3,681 which is around 18 percent of what was promised. The minimum wage was also assured to be raised to 500 dollars, but in 2023, 450 is still 50 percent less than what he offered, and like this, many plans were unfulfilled^{xx}.

Additionally, the situation may affect Ecuador's petition to exempt its citizens from Schengen visa requirements, as the lack of political stability raises concerns about the country's reliability. This, in turn, can result in a negative image of Ecuador in the eyes of the United States, potentially impacting bilateral relations and casting doubt on the credibility of discussions held between Joe Biden and Guillermo Lasso in December 2022^{xxi}.

Moreover, the allocation of state funds for candidate promotion through media channels like radio, TV, and billboards can lead to mismanagement and waste of public resources. The official page regarding the electoral finances stated that the 2021 elections alone cost around 91 million dollars, and the new elections that are going to take place in 2023 are expected to cost 79 million. This is 170 million dollars that Ecuador will have spent on elections alone in the last two years^{xxii}.

Also, the political instability caused crimes to increase. The Ecuadorian Department of Statistics, also known as INEC, shows that 6,045 more thefts happened during 2022, and motorcycle stealing was more common during that year with 5,389 more cases than usual^{xxiii}. The lack of institutional responses leads to insecurity now to perceive this. The National Comprehensive Care Service for Adults Deprived of Liberty and Juvenile Offenders (SNAI)

also has data showing that in 2021 there were 37,187 incarcerated individuals and in 2022 only 32,246^{xxiv} So the first question that comes to mind is, "How can there be fewer people deprived of freedom if there are more crimes? The answer itself is self-explanatory: the judicial function and the policy are either not working together, the police are not doing their work, or the criminals are getting out of jail.

Finally, the limited awareness and engagement of the public in reading new proposals and understanding the candidates make them more vulnerable to populism, as it was discussed prior that having 14 candidates only as presidents with different governmental plans and 14 vice presidents would be 28 profiles to study, then having to pick also the legislative members and getting to know each one of them and also picking from the major to prefect looking closely at their proposals, and also there is some popular consultation that is also mandatory to fill out and vote for and that is bidding to all of the population. Now, in 2023, the citizens are again compelled to decide between the new six presidents and vice-presidential candidates to finish the incomplete period.

It is extremely sad to think that corruption is a common phenomenon in Ecuador, regardless of the political party chosen. If you choose a head of state, you have the illusion of change, of a new direction, but if it is fatal that it does not matter whether it is a socialist, liberal, communist, or capitalist party, it has been proven that everyone follows the same scheme, the same forms of illicit enrichment. It is discouraging to see how they forget the oath they take once they take office, and how we seem condemned to the same path. The consequences of the *muerte cruzada* are fatal both nationally and internationally, but more damaging is to have evidence and know about the poor presidential management and not do anything to not assume the consequences. Now, we are facing new elections where, like all others, we have a false sense of illusion that everything will change and that the next head of state will do the right thing for his people.

ⁱ La posta. (2023, January 14). El caso el gran padrino . <https://Investigacioneslaposta.Com/>.

ⁱⁱ (Guillermo Lasso: Danilo Carrera Es Un Hombre Intachable, No Puede Ser Usado Como Símbolo De La Corrupción | Política | Noticias | El Universo, n.d.)

ⁱⁱⁱ El presidente de la república no solapa a nadie. (2023, March). Twitter, Ecuador Official Communication https://twitter.com/ComunicacionEc?ref_src=twsrc%5Etfw%7Ctwcamp%5Eetweetembed%7Ctwterm%5E1635767809970978816%7Ctwgr%5Ea6aa93bb8434022c0a753c33363d447ed3a54022%7Ctwcon%5Es1_&ref_url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.eltelegrafo.com.ec%2Fnoticias%2Factualidad%2F44%2Fpresidente-guillermo-lasso-pide-desvinculacion-dos-generales-policia-nacional

^{iv} R. (2023, April 3). Rubén Cherras: así fue su entramado empresarial y su supuesto nexos con la mafia albanesa. www.ecuavisa.com. <https://www.ecuavisa.com/la-noticia-a-fondo/ruben-cherres-asi-fue-su-entramado-empresarial-y-su-supuesto-nexo-con-la-mafia-albanesa-YK4826573>

^v *Ibidem*

^{vi} Ecuadorian Constitution, CRE, Art. 120, Official Register 449 July 24, 2008. Ecuador

^{vii} Executive Decree 741, 2023 Dissolving the legislative organ 2023, May 17 Official Register Ecuador 312

^{viii} Ecuadorian Constitution CRE, Art. 148, July 24, 2008. Ecuador

^{ix} *Ibídem*, Art 219

^x Cañizares A, 2023 June, *El presidente de Ecuador*, Guillermo Lasso, anuncia que no se postulará a una nueva elección en los comicios anticipados (The president of Ecuador, Guillermo Lasso, announces that he will not run for re-election in the upcoming early elections). <https://cnnespanol.cnn.com/2023/06/02/presidente-ecuador-guillermo-lasso-no-postulara-nueva-eleccion-comicios-anticipados-orix/>

^{xi} Organic Electoral Law, Code of Democracy Published in 2009, April 27th Official Register 578, Art. 87

^{xii} *Ibídem* Art.

^{xiii} Can political stability hurt economic growth? (2014, June 1). World Bank Blogs. <https://blogs.worldbank.org/endpovertyinsouthasia/can-political-stability-hurt-economic-growth>

^{xiv} Organic Electoral Law, Code of Democracy Published in 2009, April 27 Official Register 578, Art.47

^{xv} *Ibídem* Art 12

^{xvi} executive decree No 85, 202117 Official Register Ecuador 494. July 14`

^{xvii} PAGO EN CUENTA – Ministerio de Inclusión Económica y Social. (n.d.). PAGO EN CUENTA – Ministerio De Inclusión Económica Y Social. <https://www.inclusion.gob.ec/pago-en-cuenta/>

^{xviii} Universidad De Guayaquil . (2023, March). LINEAMIENTOS PARA LA MATRICULACIÓN DEL PERÍODO ACADÉMICO ORDINARIO CI 2023-2024. In <https://www.ug.edu.ec/planificacion/CFAP/PA/ORDINARIO/PeriodosSemestrales2023-2024/01.1%20LINEAMIENTOS%20PARA%20LA%20MATRICULACI%C3%93N%20DEL%20PERIODO%20ACAD%C3%89MICO%20ORDINARIO%20CI%202023-2024.pdf> (R-CSU-UG-SE12-098-30-03-2023). Universidad de Guayaquil.

^{xix} Un ‘check list’ a diez de las promesas del presidente Guillermo Lasso. (2023, May 23). <https://www.Eluniverso.Com/Noticias/Politica/Un-Check-List-a-Diez-de-Las-Promesas-Del-Presidente-Guillermo-Lasso-Que-Cumple-Dos-Anos-de-Mandato-Este-24-de-Mayo-Nota/>.

^{xx} *Ibídem*

^{xxi} Resumen de la reunión del Presidente Biden con el Presidente del Ecuador Guillermo Lasso. (2022, December 20). <https://Ec.Usembassy.Gov/Es/Resumen-de-La-Reunion-Del-Presidente-Biden-Con-El-Presidente-Del-Ecuador-Guillermo-Lasso/>.

^{xxii} Ministerio de Economía y Finanzas transfiere USD 3,6 millones para logística de FF.AA. en proceso electoral. (2020, November 11). In <https://www.finanzas.gob.ec/ministerio-de-economia-y-finanzas-transfiere-usd-36-millones-para-logistica-de-ff-aa-en-proceso-electoral/>. Ministerio de Economía y Finanzas .

^{xxiii} INEC. (2022, December). Estadísticas de seguridad Integral. In <https://www.ecuadorencifras.gob.ec/estadisticas/>. Instituto nacional de Estadísticas y censos.

^{xxiv} SNAI . (2022, January). Resumen Privados de libertad 2021-2022. In <https://www.atencionintegral.gob.ec/estadisticas/>. Servicio Nacional de Atención Integral a Personas Adultas Privadas de la Libertad y a Adolescentes Infractores.